

PROBLEMS OF ORGANIZATION OF STUDENTS' INDEPENDENT WORK IN THE CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM

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Abstract. *This article is about the organization of independent work of students in the credit-module system, the fact that this system creates a number of conveniences for countries, the relevance of the topic, the process of transitioning to the credit-module system of higher education institutions in our republic will eliminate a number of problematic situations.*

Keywords: *credit-module system, mentality, foreign scientists, research, scientific innovation, methodology, result, problem, independent education, foreign countries.*

Access

Currently, many reforms are being carried out in higher education institutions, and based on these reforms, in the updated credit-module system of education, the future generation will be more educated, will strengthen the knowledge they have acquired in the course of the lesson, and will be independent on themselves. performance, new technologies introduced into the educational system, all conditions are provided for students to do independent work after carefully studying foreign experiences.

In this regard, according to the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 "On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. PF-4947, in 2017-2021, higher and higher Conditions were created for the inclusion of the Bologna Declaration of Uzbekistan in the post-graduate education system, and the credit-module system was introduced in the educational process in higher education institutions. The credit-module system is a new system of training for our educational system, and specialists do not have enough knowledge in this direction. Therefore, it is an urgent issue to study the problems of independent work in the credit-module system in accordance with our own mentality based on the experience of foreign countries.

A brief analysis of the literature on the topic

Today, according to statistics, more than 50 countries of the world are based on the credit module system and are members of the Bologna declaration system. This introduced system creates a number of conveniences for these countries. Also, foreign scientists V. Pushkin, V. Topolsky, M. Gusakovskiy, D. Gubarevich, Ye. Karpiyevich, T. Krasnova, I. Osipchik and others with the problem of organizing students' independent work in the credit-module system. B. Usmanov, R. Khabibullayev, V. Orinov from the scientists of Uzbekistan. O. Rakhimov, U. Makhmonov, Q. Algarov, Q. Mirzayev, Sh. Mustafaqulov, I. The Aliyevs were involved.

Proper organization of independent education of students in the credit-module system creates the following facilities:

First, to make the learning process interesting;

Secondly, to the improvement of students' mastery;

Thirdly, to increase the responsibility of students;

Fourthly, to increase students' ability to work in a team;

Fifth, to learn to study throughout the life of students;

Sixth, it leads to the improvement of educational programs and the increase of the reputation of the higher education institution.

Relevance of the topic.

In this regard, the decision No. 824 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 31, 2020 on "Measures to improve the system related to the organization of the educational process in higher education institutions" "Higher education "On the procedure for introducing the credit-module system into the educational process in institutions" is the introduction of the credit-module system into the educational process. However, in the practical situation of this document, there are some shortcomings. In particular, there are problems in the organization of independent work of students.

The purpose of the study.

The purpose of the study is to justify the proper organization of independent education of students in the credit-module system in the higher education system.

Scientific novelty of the research. Based on advanced foreign experiences, studying the problems of organizing independent education of existing students in the credit-module system.

Research methodology. Methods of scientific knowledge such as scientific abstraction, analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, and comparative analysis were used in the research.

Research results .

On October 8, 2019, the head of our state signed the Decree "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030". In this important programmatic document, "at least 10 higher education institutions in the republic are ranked by internationally recognized organizations (Quacquarelli Symonds World University Rankings, Times Higher Education or Academic Ranking of World Universities) as higher education institutions in the first 1000 places." "and gradually transfer the educational process in higher education institutions to the credit-module system"

In order to implement these planned plans, the transition process of higher education institutions of our republic to the credit-module system requires the elimination of a number of problematic situations:

1. The one-sided approach of the management of OTMs to the implementation of the credit-module system, that is, they are busy with the implementation of only the credit part;

2. The fact that not a single regulatory document on the organization of independent education has been approved so far;

3. Time standards for organizing independent education of students and evaluating it have not been developed at the national level;

4. The status of independent education and its place in the educational process is not clear, that is, it is present in the curriculum as a percentage of hours, but neglected due to non-payment of money;

5. The question is whether teachers are ready to organize students' independent work remains open;

6. The question of whether independent work of students, which is being organized today, meets the requirements remains unanswered.

What should we pay attention to in order to solve these problems?

In the credit-module system of the management of the Higher Education Institution, the rector's will is needed to introduce independent work of students;

adapting the system to the conditions of our educational system due to the fact that the credit module system received from foreign countries is not directly compatible with our educational process;

redevelopment of documents related to the credit-module system, especially preparation and introduction of a document that fully discloses the content and essence of students' independent work;

development of time standards for the organization of student independent education and its evaluation;

the status of independent education and its place in the educational process ;

it is necessary to strengthen the teacher's responsibility in the organization of independent education, that is, to teach teachers modern types of independent education.

Conclusions and suggestions. Based on world experience, credit if students' independent work is organized correctly in the module system, i.e.:

First, students master subjects independently;

Secondly, students' theoretical knowledge increases;

Thirdly, interest in the subject being studied increases ;

Fourthly, the teacher's level of preparation for the lesson changes, that is, his responsibility increases;

Fifthly, The quality of d ars changes;

Sixth, students are employed by employers as specialists in their 4th year.

Seventh, the reputation of HEIs in front of employers will increase;

In general, based on the above, the introduction of the credit-module system in the higher education institutions of our republic forms a completely new approach and new relations in the higher education system. In order for this system to ensure the existence of a quality educational process in the educational process, on the one hand, it is necessary to establish independent education in the right way and to constantly improve it based on the needs of the times, on the other hand mutual respect, mentor-student relationship is created in the relationship between teaching professors and students. As a result, the base of the educational system of Uzbekistan on the credit-module system will form the foundation of the Third Renaissance in our republic and create an opportunity to raise an educated generation worthy of the new Uzbekistan.

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